

THE CONCEPT OF SOCIAL MORALITY IN PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY IN THE REVIEW OF WORLD PSYCHOLOGISTS.

D.R.Odilova

BPXTI magistr

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14214828>

Abstract

In this article, the formation of the teacher's social intelligence allows students to correct defects in the psychological development of the emotional and volitional sphere, to activate cognitive activity, to form knowledge, skills and abilities, to identify their social roles with those around them, and to create a social image in the social environment and independent learning. theoretical information on the interaction correction is given.

Key words: preschool age, teacher, profession, intellect, social intellect.

Relevance of the topic. The fact that the requirements for the teacher's work are quite responsible depends in many cases on social intelligence. This level allows the teacher to realize himself as a carrier of socially important information, a subject implementing social units. The formation of the teacher's social intelligence allows students to correct defects in the psychological development of the emotional and volitional sphere, to activate cognitive activity, to form knowledge, skills and abilities, to identify their social roles with those around them, and to create a social image and independent interaction in the social environment. It helps to fix the glaze.

It can be seen from this that it is important to explain the importance of social intelligence in the professional activity of the teacher by referring to the psychological aspects listed above.

However, the main theoretical approaches to assessing the characteristics of social intelligence in psychology have not yet been sufficiently defined. In this regard, it is important to consider the work of Russian psychologists

We consider it appropriate to analyze the general state of existing psychological approaches to intelligence in order to shed light on the nature of social intelligence. The approaches available to date can be listed as intelligence approaches in the following order.

There are eight main approaches to the composition and formation of intelligence, which are cited in the following scientific sources:

1. Phenomenological approach to intelligence: intelligence is considered as the main form of the content of consciousness (V. Keller; K. Dunker; M. Wertheimer; Dj. Campion, etc.).
2. Genetic approach to intelligence: intelligence is considered as a result of difficult adaptation of human interaction with the external world to the requirements of the surrounding environment in natural conditions (U.R. Charlesworth; J. Piaget).
3. Socio-cultural approach to intelligence: intelligence is the result of human socialization, as well as the purposeful influence of culture (Dj. Brunner; L. Levi-Bruhl; A.R. Luria; L.S. Vygotsky, etc.).
4. Process-active approach to intelligence: intelligence as the basic form of human activity (S.L. Rubenstein; A.V. Brushlinsky; L.A. Wenger; K.A. Abulkhanskaya-Slavskaya, etc.).

5. Educational approach to intelligence: intelligence is considered as a product of goal-oriented education (A. Staats; K. Fisher; R. Feuerstein, etc.).

6. Informational approach to intelligence: intelligence as a set of elementary processes of information processing (G. Eysenck; E. Hunt; R. Sternberg, etc.).

7. Functional-level approach to intelligence: intelligence as a system of cognitive processes at different levels (B.G. Ananov; Ye.I. Stepanova; B.M. Velichkovskii and others)

8. The regulatory approach of intelligence: intelligence as a factor of self-regulation of mental activity (L.L. Thurstone and others)

Our goal is not to in-depth analysis of the aspects specific to the nature of general approaches to intelligence and the advanced scientific ideas about them, but to shed light on the general psychological nature of intelligence, reflecting the views that it cannot exist without social development and social conditions. indicates that it is possible. Maboda representatives of the phenomenological approach, Köller, M. Wertheimer, K. Dunker, in the analysis of the content of research, development of intellect; representative of the genetic approach U.R. The consequence of Charlesworth's views is the nature of J. Piaget's operational approach: it is the socio-cultural approach that comes closest to elucidating the nature of social intelligence, and the goal-oriented educational approach cannot avoid the influence of social factors. In turn, while studying the problem of social intelligence of a person, we cannot ignore the approaches specific to other aspects of intelligence.

Our analysis of the above scientific approaches and research leads us to interpret social intelligence as a manifestation of socially beneficial adaptation. For example, the following conclusion of V. Stern, which is typical of intelligence, is consistent with our opinion, i.e., intelligence is viewed as "the general ability to adapt to new life conditions" and "the act of adaptation - solving life issues with the help of the intellect, is carried out in accordance with the predominance of consciousness over unconsciousness in thinking. will be increased" we can quote.

Another aspect that we pay attention to in our study of scientific sources is clarifying the functions of social intelligence. This issue will clarify our choice of research methods in the following paragraphs and help in the psychological analysis of the empirical materials obtained from their implementation. Research was also conducted on the functions of social intelligence (N.A. Menchinskaya (1989), Albukhanova-Slavskaya (1991), N.I. Chuprikova (1995), V.D. Shadrikov (1997) and others (8; 60). we will be able to explain the functions of social intelligence on the basis of double conditioning.

According to the above-mentioned studies, as well as the theoretical analysis of psychological-pedagogical literature, the following functions are distinguished: knowledge-evaluation, communicative-valuable, reflexive-corrective. Now let's take a look at the summary of these functions. The cognitive-evaluation function is manifested in the process of socialization, in the determination of the content of interpersonal interaction, the real help of others, in the determination of individual opportunities for the achievement of activity results. Accordingly, social intelligence provides the necessary information processing to predict the results of activities. On the one hand, a person receives information about the nature of other people's activities, understands it and subjugates it in performing mental operations. On the other hand, it leads to the formation of conclusions about the importance of what is happening in the process of information processing.

N.A. According to Mechinskaya (1989), information can be positive and accepted, or, on the contrary, negative and rejected. In both cases, we have to show mental activity related to a certain pace of information processing. The obtained information ensures the manifestation of evaluation conclusions about the possibility of its use, the level of real achievement of results. This leads Islam to understand oneself and one's existence in the process of self-realization. In this process, a person manifests himself as a subject of learning activity. Intellectual capabilities and social conditions of mastering experience are acquired in accordance with the purpose. Thus, in order to manifest himself as a subject of the implementation of this function (from the aspect of knowledge), he forms evaluative judgments about what is happening in the process of selecting information suitable for the conditions, setting a goal (the aspect of evaluation). However, this function occurs during the implementation of the next function, and its cost of achievement may not allow to determine.

The next communicative-valuable function of social intelligence depends on the need to understand others and, in turn, to be understood by them. Self-awareness in constant communication with other people begins with the process of actively distinguishing and mastering the standards and standards of human interaction. N.I. According to Chuprikova (1995), communication is manifested in the ability to convey the content of expressing one's situation, attitude to the interlocutor and the listener, as a result, to show the purpose of the message. In addition, on the one hand, we look at communication as a way of establishing a connection between a person and the social environment, and on the other hand, as a process of searching for the meaning of the valuable environment of life. Appropriately, we divide the communicative-valuable function into two main manifestations.

Creating a plan of ideal content (the content of communication) is related to determining the social action situation of adaptation to the understanding of this person. A person does not react to nothing and does not perceive information, but puts forward issues related to social relations, perceives, understands the social-psychological and personal position of people and puts himself and him in his place. does it through imagination. Relying on the scientific observations recorded in psychological sources, social intelligence adapts a person to society, that is, to the environment in which he lives and is recognized as a representative of his social environment; we can say that it is a set of abilities that help to effectively implement interpersonal and professional relations. In turn, the term social intelligence refers to the ability to understand oneself, behavior, and other people in the process of interaction with other people, and to implement effective interaction and achieve a set goal. intends to develop the well. It is also necessary to remember that social intelligence plays an important role in the socialization of a person, education, and the implementation of intercultural communication.

References:

- 1.Nishanova, Z.T.Rivojlanish psixologiyasi. Pedagogik psixologiya [Matn] : darslik / Z.T. Nishanova va boshq. - Toshkent: « O 'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati» nashriyoti, 2018. - 600b.
- 2.<https://uza.uz/oz/>
- 3.Рублева, Н. В. Проблема развития социального интеллекта в процессе социального воспитания детей старшего дошкольного возраста / Н. В. Рублева. — Текст :

- непосредственный // Педагогическое мастерство : материалы I Междунар. науч. конф. (г. Москва, апрел 2012 г.). — Москва : Буки-Веди, 2012. — С. 127-130. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/conf/ped/archive/22/2238/> (дата обращения: 23.03.2024).
- 4.Kubyshkina M.L. Ijtimoiy muvaffaqiyat motivi//Psixologiyaning nazariy va amaliy masalalari (shaxs parametrlari). Sankt-Peterburg 1996 yil (2-son, 2-qism, 39-45 b)
- 5.Roziqova, M. (2023). Baynalminal oilalarning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari. Interpretation and researches, 1(1).
- 6.Дилмуродова, З. (2023). Развитие способностей детей младшего школьного возраста. Актуальные проблемы обучения социально-гуманитарных наук в медицинском образовании, 1(1), 487-493.
- 7.Абдулина О.А. Общепедагогическая подготовка учителя в системе высшего педагогического образования. -М.: Просвещение,1990.-141с.
- 8.Аминов Н.А. Социальный интеллект и социальная компетенция в подготовке социальных работников (факторные модели Дж. Гилфорда и Г. Марлоу) //Социальная работа /Ред. И.А. Зимняя. Вып.5. М.,1992. -С.37-46.
- 9.Баратов Ш.Р. Социально-психологические основы создания психологической службы в Узбекистане: Автореф. дис. ... докт. психол. наук. – Ташкент: 1998. - 37 с.
- 10.Борисова Е.М. О роли профессиональной деятельности в формировании личности //Психология формирования и развития личности /отв. ред. Л.И.Анциферова. М.: Изд-во Наука. - С. 159-176.
- 11.Avezov O.R. Psyshologisal relations between family members. Ssientifis Journal Impast Fastor. VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 2. ISSN 2181-1784. SJIF 2022: 5.947 February 2022 www.oriens.uz. P-945-949
- 12.Avezov O.R. Mental Status and Behavioral Reastions in Emergensity. and Extreme Emergencies AMERISAN JOURNAL OF SOSIAL AND HUMANITARIAN RESEARSH. ISSN: 2690-9626 Vol.3, No 1, 2022. <https://www.grnjournals.us/index.php/AJSHR/artisle/view/714>
- 13.Avezov O.R., SH.R. Barotov, L.YA. Olimov. Psixologiya nazariyasi va tarixi. Darslik. "O'zbekiston faylasuflari jamiyati" nashriyoti. Toshkent. 2019 yil. 492 bet.
- 14.Avezov O.R. L.YA. Olimov, A.M. Nazarov. Shaxs psixologiyasi. Darslik. "Durдона" nashriyoti Buxoro. 2019 yil. 340 bet.
- 15.Zilola Dilmurodova. Международная конференция академических наук 3 (6), 66-72, 2024
- 16.Dilmurodova, Z. . (2024). SHAXS QOBILIYATINI ERTA ANIQLASHNING MUHIM JIHATI. Наука и инновация, 2(17), 84–87. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/si/article/view/33853>
- 17.Dilmurodova Z.D. (2023). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSH O'QUVCHILAR QOBILIYATI VA QIZIQISHLAR PSIXODIAGNOSTIKASI. Экономика и социум, (12 (115)-1), 202-205.
- 18.Abduqodirova D., Pardaboyeva M. THE ROLE OF EMOTIONAL CREATIVITY IN STUDENTS'DECISION-MAKING //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND SOCIAL-HUMANITARIAN SCIENCES. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 7. – С. 27-30.